

THE MOTIF OF THE CITY IN S. AFLATUNI'S PROSE**Polovinkina Tatyana Viktorovna**

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Abstract. *in Aflatuni prose, the urban motif is studied mainly through social, cultural and spiritual aspects. The city, its population composition, management system, social strata, architecture and economic life occupy a central place in the stories. Aflatuni attempts to portray an ideal society through the urban motif, in which justice, human rights, knowledge and spirituality are central. Through various aspects of urban life, such as markets, decision-making assemblies, schools, situations that occur in religious and philosophical environments, social networks and communication between people are analyzed. Aflatuni, especially in his work "the Republic", shows the structure of an ideal society through the urban motif, its principles of governance and its moral foundations. The city, at the same time, is presented as an environment that educates and maintains justice, knowledge and spirituality. Through these motifs, Aflatuni presents a methodology of thought aimed at the organization of society and its development.*

Keywords: Aflatuni, City, civilization, modernity, Plato.

МОТИВ ГОРОДА В ПРОЗЕ С. АФЛАТУНИ

Аннотация. *в прозе Афлатуни городской мотив рассматривается в основном через социальные, культурные и духовные аспекты. Город, его состав населения, система управления, социальные слои, архитектура и экономическая жизнь занимают центральное место в рассказах. Афлатуни пытается изобразить идеальное общество с помощью городского мотива, в котором центральное место занимают справедливость, права человека, знания и духовность. Анализируются различные аспекты городской жизни, такие как рынки, собрания по принятию решений, школы, ситуации, возникающие в религиозной и философской среде, социальные сети и общение между людьми. Афлатуни, особенно в своей работе "Республика", показывает структуру идеального общества через городской мотив, принципы управления и моральные устои. В то же время город представлен как среда, которая воспитывает и поддерживает справедливость, знания и духовность. Посредством этих мотивов Афлатуни представляет методологию мышления, направленную на организацию общества и его развитие.*

Ключевые слова: Афлатуни, Город, цивилизация, современность, Платон.

Introduction

The Nasrid dynasty ruled southern Spain in the 13th and 15th centuries, especially the Nasrid state of Granada. During the dynasty, the culture, art and architecture of Spanish Muslims reached its peak. Motifs within the cities and towns created during the Nasrid period were also of special importance. There are many scientific studies of the famous Alhambra Palace in Granada, Nasrid architecture and its urbanization style. A review of the connections between cities of the Nasrid period with Aflatuni or Plato's motifs about the city makes it possible to produce a complete picture of the culture and philosophy of this period.

S. Aflatuni and its urban motifs

The urban motif in Aflatuni prose can be seen through its prism of philosophical understanding and symbolism. Aflatuni or Sergei Aflatunov (pseudonym) was a famous writer, whose works were distinguished by a deep philosophical approach and attention to the inner world of man. In his works, the city often manifests itself not only as a place of action, but also as a metaphor for the state of society, human life and its various aspects.

The city can be a symbol of chaos, civilization, modernity, but at the same time a place of spiritual search, isolation or utopian ideal. In such texts, the city is often not a background for events, but an important part of the semantic structure that plays a role in opening up themes of loneliness, in the search for the meaning of life and in moral disputes. The urban motif in Aflatuni prose can also be associated with the study of conflicts between the individual and society, the development of the individual in urbanization and the pressure of the social environment.

In some cases, the city may reflect a place of opportunity and alienation that is rapidly changing and often difficult to find its place in a soulless world. For a deeper analysis, it is necessary to refer to specific works in order to clearly consider how this motive is carried out in the context of the author's general worldview.

Socrates, Plato and Aristotle are the greatest representatives of ancient Greek philosophy, who influenced many areas in human history. In Plato's "The State", Urban motifs have a special place, in which visions of an ideal state and the structure of society are advanced. The main values of the city of Plato were Justice, the quality management of government and the role of citizens in society. Plato's ideas about the city therefore took their toll on the culture of the following centuries.

While the architecture and urbanism of the Nasrid dynasty were not influenced by Plato's ideal city ideas, the construction of the city and its approach to its structure show a number of similarities. The cities built during the Nasrid period, notably the city of Granada and the Alhambra Palace, are characterized by their elaborate and beautiful architecture. It is at the heart of architecture and urban planning:

1. Harmony: in Alhambra Palace and other Nasrid architectural examples, the harmony between the natural environment, design and structures is highlighted. Of special importance in the construction of cities were their location, water sources and interactions.
2. Philosophical elements: in the cities of the Nasrids, especially in public places, there were elements aimed at maintaining mutual balance. This focuses on Justice, sympathy and spiritual importance in the organization of the city.
3. Water and gardens: in a unique way in Alhambra, great importance is attached to the waters. Waterways, fountains and gardens played an important role in ensuring the welfare of the community. These elements are similar to Plato's idea of ensuring justice in the "state" and harmony with nature.
4. Social stratification and the system of governance: the structure of society under the Nasrids, their division into social strata, was also similar to the visions in Plato's "the state". The interaction and social role of citizens was important in the Nasrid cities, but the influence of the rulers was also very great.

The Alhambra Palace is one of the most striking examples of Nasrid architecture. The interior and exterior spaces of the Palace show a high level of harmony of architecture and art. Plato's ideas about justice and order were embodied through the cities and structures built during the Nasrid period. The interior decoration and exterior architecture of the Alhambra Palace, with its intricate symmetry and rigor, show that Plato implemented the basic principles of the ideal city. Water and green spaces, fountains and gardens also each have their own spiritual and educational significance.

Conclusion

The study of communication between cities of the Aflatuni (Plato) and the Nasrid period, the peculiarities of ancient Greek philosophy and the archival and urban planning direction of the Nasrid period are well understood. The cities of the Nasrid period, at the same time the Alhambra Palace in Granada, with its complex, beautiful and spiritually child construction, stand out as a unique legacy of the human studies of the retirement age, but not the whole.

REFERENCES

1. Афлатуни – Сухбат Афлатуни. Глиняные буквы, плывущие яблоки: Журнал «Октябрь» М. 2006.
2. Османова З.Г.-Литература путешествий как духовное самопознание личности. Тимур Зульфикаров: Земные и запредельные странствия поэта История национальных литератур. М. 1996.С .18
3. Зульфикаров –«Земные и небесные странствия».Т. 1990.С. 31.
4. Томилова, Н.А-. Дerviши как учитель в современной русской литературе: на примере повести Сухбата Афлатуни «Глиняные буквы, плывущие яблоки» Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики.М. 2012.